

PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES AND THEIR DYNAMICS METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: *In the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the further development of physical education and sports. During the research, a number of methods and technologies were used to obtain complete information about the psychophysical and psychological-pedagogical condition of young people with spinal cord injuries in using wheelchairs, their dynamics.*

Key words: *social adaptation, adaptive physical activity, spinal cord injury, movement disorder.*

Аннотация: *В Республике Узбекистан особое внимание уделяется дальнейшему развитию физической культуры и спорта. В ходе исследования был использован ряд методов и технологий, позволяющих получить полную информацию о психофизическом и психолого-педагогическом состоянии молодых людей с травмами позвоночника при использовании инвалидных колясок, их динамике.*

Ключевые слова: *социальная адаптация, адаптивная двигательная активность, позвоночно-спинномозговая травма, двигательные нарушения.*

INTRODUCTION

With the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a gradual rise in all areas, fundamental physical, political and spiritual changes, renewal in the system of universal human values, all personal needs, demands and interests of a person are brought to the fore, especially It is no secret today that the spiritual, moral and physical capabilities of the younger generation are increasing.

In this regard, an important direction of the complex and multifaceted problem of raising a new person is to inculcate in each person the culture of self-care about his health. In order to find it, family, pre-school institutions, school, secondary special vocational education system, neighborhood, health, physical education and sports system employees use all their energy and enthusiasm to teach the child from youth to physical education. they need to absorb the love that they have.

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Today, the issue of social protection is based on the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 1, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of support for persons with disabilities at the state level" in 2017-2021. It is being implemented in accordance with the tasks defined in the Strategy of Actions in the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In recent years, one of the most important tasks in our Republic is the development of mass sports. The task of educating mentally healthy generations and future patriots of independent Uzbekistan ultimately falls on teachers and specialists. In accordance with the "National Personnel Training Program" implemented in our country, it is the development of the physical and mental health of the growing young generation, the desire for a healthy lifestyle and inculcating the love of love.

DOLLARITY OF SUBJECT.

Today, the process of democratization is actively changing in our society, which determines the urgency of searching for new organizational and

methodological approaches in solving the problems of social adaptation of persons with health disabilities.

Physical culture and sports, regardless of the level of mobility limitations, create opportunities for the integral biological social self-fulfillment of a person, and allow a better understanding of motor ability and its social role as a factor in the formation of advanced socio-cultural policies in relation to different groups. will give.

We use wheelchairs to create the necessary conditions for free social activity and movement of population groups, especially people with spinal cord injury, which is one of the main components of their normal social adaptation and integration. Adaptive physical culture and sports are the most attractive form of social integration for people with spinal cord injuries.

The purpose of the study is to scientifically justify and experimentally prove the effectiveness of the use of Adaptive physical education tools aimed at strengthening the social adaptation of young disabled people with spinal cord injuries who use wheelchairs.

18 disabled students with spinal cord injuries who use wheelchairs were included in our study. Their age ranged from 18 to 27 years. Prescription for traumatic spinal injury is not less than 7 years. All subjects have II disability according to the main disease and various related diseases according to the classification (spinal cord injury disease).

Mobility impairments in people with spinal cord injuries are not limited to the inability to walk without assistive devices. Disruption of postural tonic muscles, reflected in the inability to maintain the vertical position of the body without additional support, significantly limits the motor abilities of the upper extremities, makes it difficult for self-service, the development of new motor skills, reduces the level of social activity, which is o leads to significant deterioration of the quality of life of the studied contingent and limited possibilities of social adjustment.

Among other methods, during the study, we developed and implemented a method for assessing the social adjustment index.

Based on the results of the determined experiment, we have developed a comprehensive program of social adaptation of young disabled people with spinal cord injury using Adaptive physical education.

The experimental program consisted of three main stages:

- restoration of postural tonic muscle activity;
- formation of sufficient tool base and functional capabilities;
- increase the level of social activity;

Trainings according to the experimental program were held in the form of lessons three times a week for half an hour.

In the process of social adaptation of young disabled people who use wheelchairs and have spinal cord injuries, the teaching conditions and organizational-methodical features of the use of adaptive physical education tools were determined.

Comparison of morphofunctional indices in the research group, after the experiment compared with the control group, improvement of the following characteristics was ensured:

- formation of vital capacity along with the use of a large number of aerobic exercises and various breathing exercises during the year cycle of the experimental program;
- the indicators of the study of heart rate variability show a significant improvement of the mechanisms of regulating the work of the heart after the training experiment conducted in the research group.

As a result of the research program, there were significant changes in the level of physical fitness of the subjects, as well as in many indices:

- the time to cover a short distance in a wheelchair is significantly improved, which characterizes the ability to increase speed;
- as a result of the experiment, it was found that the speed and strength indicators of the upper limbs and body increased significantly. The genesis of the motor profile

indices of disabled people with spinal cord injury was determined, as a result of which an educational experience using Adaptive physical education tools was conducted.

- in the resulting studies, the Adaptive Physical Education Test revealed significant differences in favor of the experimenter between the control group and the study group.

Along with the significant improvement of the social adaptation index during the obtained study, a significant increase in the strength of the correlation between the indicators describing the motor abilities and the indicators of social adaptation was found, which is the level of motor disorders and the social integration of people with spinal cord injuries who use wheelchairs. confirms the assumption that it is related to the level.

A study of the interrelationships between different indicators of mobility skills in wheelchair users of spinal cord injuries and the resulting studies show the importance of the degree of development of postural tonic muscles.

CONCLUSION.

Corrective measures and step-by-step training of young people with disabilities caused by spinal cord injuries completed the courses based on the program developed on the basis of the use of adaptive physical education tools, and the increase in the total time of motor movements has been proven to be effective for functional status. It ensures the necessary recovery of the body and motor base of disabled students with spinal cord injuries, improves the psycho-emotional state, which significantly improves the quality of life, effectively improves the level of social adaptation, and fully solves the issues of social integration.

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